

Recommended citation: Schmitt, F., Frielingsdorf, S., Nojoumi, S., Friedrich, T., & Budisa, N. (2021). Courses based on competitions highly motivate students for research-based learning. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 461-474). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14647073.

COURSES BASED ON COMPETITIONS HIGHLY MOTIVATE STUDENTS FOR RESEARCH-BASED LEARNING

FJ Schmitt¹

Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg
Halle, Germany

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9058-5804>

S Frielingsdorf

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

S Nojumi

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6325-468X>

T Friedrich

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

N Budisa

University of Manitoba
Winnipeg, Canada

Conference Key Areas: *Challenge based education, Attractiveness and future engineering skills*

Keywords: *iGEM • Synthetic Biology • Research Based Teaching • Project learning*

ABSTRACT

Specially designed research-based learning (RBL) modules are highly motivating, especially when they are based on competitions. We designed a project module at Technische Universität Berlin to motivate students from all fields to get involved in synthetic biology and evaluated the perception by our students and the marks they achieved in a final oral exam. During five years we experienced highly successful student groups that won prizes on the international student competitions iGEM and BIOMOD in Boston and San Francisco. The student teams organized themselves and invested strong efforts over long time periods to achieve their ambitious self

¹ *Corresponding Author:*

FJ Schmitt

franz-josef.schmitt@physik.uni-halle.de

chosen goals during the projects. The comparison between evaluation results and marks showed that the students achieved a high competence level.

We conclude that RBL modules which are coupled with competitions are highly motivating. Our experience shows that international student competitions like iGEM or BIOMOD represent an excellent basis for designing RBL courses in synthetic biology and biotechnology. Since the teams were interdisciplinary also students from informatics, engineering, physics, chemistry, mathematics and even arts were involved, successfully. The aim of the study is to present both 1) the methodological concept to set up similar competition and research based learning modules and 2) the outcome of our evaluation and the marks which are obtained by the students.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Combined competition and research-based learning (RBL)

We believe training should comply with Humboldt's ideal, which we conceive as: *teaching without research is empty and research without teaching is blind*. In that sense we believe that learning is most motivating when it combines both, 1) the thirst for experiences and understanding and 2) the methodology of a researcher.

Therefore, we designed the student centered and competition based research module “iGEM-Synthetic Biology” where young students from all backgrounds with little or no research experience are provided with the intellectual and scientific resources to become confident, responsible, independent researchers of a group that targets a highly specialized field that needs a broad range of competencies.

Student-centered courses, projects and workshops that enable students to design their own research program, which can later be presented in a competition, are by nature highly motivating and of great didactic, scientific and societal value [2, 3].

RBL experienced a rise in its didactic awareness in the last 20 years [4, 5]. In our own RBL module “iGEM – Synthetic Biology” we observed an extraordinary motivation of the students and we believe that this is activated by the combination of RBL with a competition [6, 7] and an oral final exam that targets the basic teaching matter.

Generally, the following criteria motivate students to be highly active and drive them to achieve extraordinary results: (I) a democratic, student-centered structure, (II) a project of relevance targeting current societally important questions of e.g. sustainable waste treatment or energy production, (III) public science communication (as performed, e.g. during the *Long Night of the Sciences* and student-centered conferences, on a regular basis) and (IV) the participation in competitions. The motivation to achieve something really substantial, to obtain a product, that helps to save the world in their own point of view, is outstanding and is hardly achieved in other teaching formats [2, 3]. This especially accounts for a novel and fascinating research field like Synthetic Biology that constructs novel building blocks in biology [8], intending to find and understand new forms of life [9] which are unknown to date [10 - 12].

1.2 Research-based learning (RBL) from a cognitive science point of view

An extremely important question which needs to be addressed by universities is how to educate young students enabling them to solve real societal problems such as climate change or social cohesion. Knowledge and competence emerge from a development process, as psychological studies [13, 14] and error research [15, 16] show. The finally achieved competence levels are ordered hierarchically according to Bloom's taxonomy [17]. Each level requires exercise and self-reflection combined with the phantasy to drive basic concepts further enabling creative processes [18].

Therefore, RBL project courses provide a chance to reshape the teaching environment especially when developing new concepts, and potentially satisfy the need to achieve core competencies, which endow students with the capability to master problems occurring later in their professional life. These problem-related competences should gain higher priority in academic teaching and new didactic strategies need to be developed. This applies both to theoretical subjects [19, 20, 21], and experimental subjects (e.g. practical courses) [20, 22] linked to RBL [2, 3, 6, 7, 22-25].

1.3 Elements of digital teaching and presentation skills

Digitalization plays a major role in the communication of individual work or general science including the acquisition of and the search for knowledge. It enables a quick literature search, the administration and sharing of information and the collaborative documentation including the recording of actions and progress. Secondly, digitalization can support self-directed learning [26 - 28]. Thirdly, digitalization offers transfer possibilities between disciplines and institutions as well as towards the public when research outcome and learning content is shared in social networks, on blogs or via videos. Competence development that is urgently needed to handle future challenges include self-regulation issues [28 - 32], identification of learning strategies [33], rating of information quality and relevance and interest development [34, 35]. In this context, it is promising to record the students' current experiences and behavior in a timely manner in the respective actual situation, and, if necessary, to intervene in a controlling manner (ambulatory assessment) [36, 37].

In "iGEM-Synthetic Biology" the students participate in international competitions like iGEM or BIOMOD [6,7], where they present their work with a talk, a website that needs to contain a complete documentation of their laboratory work and a three-minute video (for BIOMOD) that attractively covers the relevant steps of the project [38]. In addition the students organize the large project with project management tools like Trello® or Slack® to track their progress, distribute responsibilities and conduct project reviews. As the students are also judged by the efficiency of their science communication they set up facebook, twitter and Instagram accounts to steady post news on their projects. In such sense RBL is naturally suitable to activate digital competences of the students if that is initiated at the beginning of the project.

Fig. 1. The 2016/17 team “multibrane” outside and inside the lab.

Presentation skills are part of the entire project as the students organize individual presentations in their seminars. By attending scientific meetings like the Forsch2017 conference at Humboldt University of Berlin, especially designed for student project presentations, or the urban and national “Long Night of the Sciences”, where their work is presented to up to 3000 people (2019) in an open science communication format, science communication skills are developed further.

Finally, at the competition’s jamboree, the students present their results creatively on stage in form of a kind of theater play combined with a scientific talk (similar to a science slam).

2 CONCEPT AND METHODS OF “IGEM - SYNTHETIC BIOLOGY”

2.1 How to start?

We introduced “iGEM - Synthetic Biology” in 2014/15 and the module took place five times until 2018/19 with 10-15 participants for two semesters and three supervisors that invested an equivalent of 8 SWS (teachinghours per week and semester) all together. The students achieve an equivalent of 9 ECTS credits according to an overall effort of 270 working hours. The module teaches the basics of synthetic biology while students perform complex laboratory work to achieve their self developed project goal, they discuss their results with the public and present afterwards at an international competition (iGEM or BIOMOD [6, 7]).

At the beginning the supervisors distribute the task to all participants to present winner projects of former years and/or recent research papers (usually discussed by the winner teams) during the seminar talks. The time schedule of the seminar and the digital project management tools are established. All in all, the students refer to the current state of science but they are already try to think beyond – not necessarily with the focus on a deep scientific approach but in a broader sense of how to transfer recent scientific findings to more general or even different problems. This partially involves a

kind of “science fiction”, however, it helps to find novel approaches. The supervisors seem to be visionary in that sense that they trigger the students’ ideas during the seminar.

Once a topic has been chosen, the participants formulate a hypothesis and a proposal for research, a realistic goal and concrete research methods. The students do online research and use their project management software and the web page for online documentation, project design, project tasks and documentation [2, 3, 20, 22, 23]. The Digital documentation also enables the supervisors for ambulatory assessment. From that content the student teams post on the internet (facebook [39], twitter [40], instagram [41]) and to develop the blog and video on the project.

2.2 How to design the final exam?

We decided to hold an oral final exam with each student to ensure that the basic teaching matter of the module is recognized and the work on their own project leads to a visible growth of professional competence. Therefore the competition is not the mandatory requirement to finalize the module but it is the final exam. Large numbers of questions of the students on the exam and the teaching matter and an excellent average performance during the final exams showed us that the students also wanted to perform in the final exam and not in the competition only. We even believe that these motivations to achieve both, a good rating in the competition and also in the final exam, are linked. A didactic study on the possible correlations of motivations and causes of achieved core competences might be still elusive. At the current point we can just contribute with the objective evaluation of the students performance during the final exam which is described in chapter 4 together with the evaluation of the module by the students themselves.

2.3 How to progress with the team?

Once the project idea is crystallized, the most important issue is to provide a framework for project implementation. Wet laboratory research in engineering biology is always difficult already at this level, even when simple protocols and procedures are followed. The research project is carried out as a team of usually 10-15 participants, who subdivide into different task groups. At the beginning of the project, the participants indicate which skills and which specialist knowledge they bring in, and which tasks they would like to work on. Ideally, there is one qualified expert per task group who takes over responsibility and shares his/her knowledge with the others in the group. The experiments carried out in the laboratory are first recorded in a laboratory book and then transferred into digital form on the project website. This also ensures open and transparent science and promotes the idea of OpenData and OpenAccess which are principles of the initiators of iGEM and BIOMOD.

2.4 Strengths and weaknesses

As outlined we believe that the main strength of the module that combines RBL with a competition and a final exam is an extraordinary high motivation to learn both, science communication and professional competences. However a disadvantage might be that

the participation in the competition which was linked with a travel to San Francisco (BIOMOD) or Boston (iGEM) is a driving motivation and overshadows the need to learn the basic teaching matter. We addressed this by motivating the students to care themselves on the acquisition of financial support. The students were finally supported by companies (Bayer), working groups and cooperation partners as well as the Cluster of Excellence “UniSysCat” (funded by DFG) and the “Society of the Friends of TU Berlin e.V.”. In addition it is useful to clarify at the beginning that the participation in the competition is not to be sure but depends on the quality of the project progress and the individual engagement during the project. As both, iGEM and BIOMOD were conducted online during the Covid-19 pandemic a pure online participation in these competition would be an opportunity to shift the focus from expensive travels to performance in competitions and exams.

2.5 Happy end and beyond?

During the BIOMOD competition in San Francisco, the 2017 project “Multibrane” won a gold medal and the third place worldwide in the categories “best project” and “best video” [42]. During the final phase of the competition, the students spent several weeks working intensively every day in the laboratory and optimized their internet presence until late in the evening to realize the ultimate success at the BIOMOD competition.

It turned out that the students show a high motivation to work on their remarkably elaborate projects with great efforts in and around the laboratory (see Fig. 2). The module was awarded the prize for excellent teaching of the Society of Friends of the TU Berlin e.V. 2018 [43].

Fig. 2. “iGEM – Synthetic Biology” students working in the laboratory at TUB (see acknowledgements). Reprinted with permission from [25]

In 2019, TUB has included “iGEM – Synthetic Biology” into a large campaign initiated by the vice-president for teaching, Prof. Hans-Ulrich Hei, with the special focus on RBL.

3 EXAMPLE PROJECTS

3.1 The 2015/2016 and 2016/2017 project “MultiBrane”

In 2017, the highly interdisciplinary student team "MultiBrane" with participating students from bachelor and master programs of biotechnology, chemistry, physics, informatics, biochemistry, mechanical engineering and arts as well as bachelor students from the orientation study program “MINT^{grün}” at TUB worked together and won the third place worldwide in the BIOMOD competition [44] (See Fig. 1). They designed a modular biological membrane designed with active fusion proteins for claring water from pollutants such as microplastics, antibiotics and heavy metals by binding suitable enzymes to the membrane [45 - 48] (See Fig. 3). They characterized their construct exhaustively by integrating the green fluorescent protein to apply fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy which is especially suitable to characterize fluorescent hybrid systems [49 - 53].

Fig. 3 Concept of the multibrane as developed by the 2016/17 Student team to combine different proteins for clearing water from pollutants such as microplastics, antibiotics and heavy metals on a membrane of bacterial cellulose

3.2 The 2017/2018 and 2018/19 project “smart B.O.B.”

In the semester 2017/18 the team was driven with the idea to replace fossil fuels and other environmentally harmful energy sources by renewable technologies involving genetically modified photosynthetic bacteria. As supervisors we suggested the students an actual approach proposed by Haas et al. [54]. The electrons released from photosynthesis should be fed into an electrical circuit. With different approaches, it was planned to optimize this process [55], i.e. by genetic engineering of a more efficient electron transport chain to the extracellular space [56] or to improve adhesion of the bacteria to the metal electrodes [49]. The final definition of the theme took quite a long time as the students proposed a large variety of visionary projects which were discussed in detail with the supervisors. So in 2018 we decided not to participate in the competition but shift the participation to the BIOMOD 2019 competition. The first

idea was the development of a hierarchically structured fuel cell, where stable populations of two different species grow on nanostructured electrodes, with one species producing hydrogen driven by incident solar light, and another species directly generating an enhanced electrochemical reduction potential by heterotrophic growth in a hydrogen-rich atmosphere [57]. However, after studies of current literature on the complexity of synergistic growth and cooperative evolution in limited environments, the team decided to focus on the growth of a single organism only.

So the team “smart B.O.B.” (“smart biologically-optimized battery”) formed and developed the concept of a biological battery containing photosynthetic cyanobacteria able to generate electricity due to potential changes on macroscopic electrodes (see Fig. 4). In detail, according to the concept of an electrochemical workstation as e.g. technically proposed by the group of Adir [55], carbon membranes or a carbon mesh can be used as a conductive matrix to house electrochemically active bacteria that are well characterized and can therefore be genetically manipulated. Similar approaches of conductive and nutrient carrying matrices for bacterial growth have just recently been proposed as suitable reactors for biological batteries [55, 56, 58] (See Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Left side: Basic idea of a biological battery driven by photoautotrophic cyanobacteria, right side: Simplified construction of an electrochemical growth cell based on commercially available “mud watts” [58]. Reprinted with permission from [25].

Fig. 5. The growth cell under illumination and the setup suitable to monitor current and voltage during on-off periods of illumination.

4 EVALUATION RESULTS AND ACHIEVED COMPETENCES

Fig. 6. Part of the evaluation results 2017/18 (n=15).

The project “iGEM - Synthetic Biology” has been repeatedly evaluated from different sides (TUB and *tuprojects* coordination) very positively. In particular, the lecture style and competence of the participating experts as well as the teaching style of the lecturers who worked rather as team members than as teachers were rated in the highest possible category. Most importantly we were interested in students evaluation of their competence growth. It turned out that the module was estimated (ranging from very good = 1 to very bad = 4) with 1.6 in understandability of the study matter and scientific level. Ranging from 1 = very appropriate to 4 = very inappropriate the quantity of the teaching matter was rated 1.3 with a bit lower ranking of 1.9 for the structure of the module. Usability of the learned and Interest in the topic was extremely positively rated at 1.1 with motivation to get deeper into the matter ranking at 1.2. Interest rise during the module participation was lower with 1.7 but on a high level. So we conclude that the students judged their interest and the assumed usability and importance of the taught matter at highest level. They feel comfortable with the scientific level and the quantity and understandability of the matter even in such an interdisciplinary team which focusses on molecular biology. This is in contrast to the fact that the students worked even more in the laboratory and for the preparation of their blog, presentations and the teaching video as they would have needed to achieve the credit points of the

module. The students are somehow missing the structure of the teaching module which might be caused by the nature of such a student centered teaching module.

All students finished the module with an oral exam and they were asked deep into the matter of synthetic biology. The 15 students in 2017/18 obtained marks between 1.0 (best mark in a range from 1.0 to 4.0) and 1.7. The average mark was 1.15 and the involved supervisors were regularly astonished by the deep knowledge obtained by the students during their time of participation ranging from 9 months up to 2 years (2 semesters (2x3 months with 3 months break inbetween) were mandatory).

From the students' side, the module was recommended to 100% for participation. Importantly, another point of the students' criticism was that they wanted even more interaction with experts from the working groups as they felt highly inspired by their competent input.

Acknowledgements

Work was funded by the Society of Friends of TU Berlin e.V., the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) within the framework of the QPL project WIMIplus (SynTUBio) and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC 2008 – 390540038 – UniSysCat. NB thanks Canada Research Chairs Program (Grant No. 950-231971) for support. Further support was provided by the Institute of Chemistry. We highly acknowledge all student participants since 2017: Bene Bohnen, Franziska Graeger, Caroline Hamelmann, Fabian Krüger, Sophia Kunze, Jonathan Lefebre, Florian Meissner, Alexandra Preußner, Isabel Schuman, Sebastian Sperber, Fiona Wahl, My Vu, Saskia Bundschuh, Lea Losch, Dominik Bierbaum, Wibke Gronewald, Boyang Huang, Pauline Kautz, Lisa Budzinski, Nikolaj Koch, Hannah Aring, Nico Borgsmüller, Zac Taylor, Sandor Adam, Sandra Zipfel, Fabian Toeppke, Leon Plath, John Tu, Thu Ha Dang as well as Johann Bauerfeind for his engagement in 2015 and Tobias Baumann for supervision of the 2017 iGEM Team "MultiBrane". Florian Schmitt is acknowledged for his artwork in Fig. 4 and 5. We thank the Institute of Chemistry/Technical University of Berlin for an extremely dynamic environment that has promoted our intellectual development and inspired us to make important decisions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Acevedo-Rocha, CG, Budisa, N (2016), Xenomicrobiology: a roadmap for genetic code engineering, *Microbial Biotechnology*, Vol. 9, pp. 666–676
- [2] Schmitt, F-J, Schröder, C, Yenice Campbell, Z, Wilkening, S, Moldenhauer, M, Friedrich, T (2017), Self-dependent students in transdisciplinary projects tend to higher interest in sustainability research, Education Excellence for Sustainable Development, SEFI Annual Conference 2017, pp. 25-32
- [3] Schmitt, F-J, Yenice Campbell, Z, Graeger, F, Frielingsdorf, S, Lefebre, J, Budisa, N (2019), Studierendenzentrierte Projekte nach dem Prinzip des forschenden Lernens

stiften hohe Motivation, Tagungsband zum 4. Symposium zur Hochschullehre in den MINT-Fächern, Nürnberg, pp. 85-93

[4] Huber, L, Hemmer, J, Schneider, F (2009), *Forschendes Lernen im Studium. Aktuelle Konzepte und Erfahrungen*. UVW Universitäts Verlag, Bielefeld 2009

[5] Ifenthaler, D, Gosper, M (2014), *Research Based Learning – Connecting Research and Instruction*, in: *Curriculum Models for the 21st Century* (Eds.: Ifenthaler, D, Gosper, M), Springer, New York, pp. 73-89.

[6] web page: https://igem.org/Main_Page, accessed on 2021-07-07

[7] web page: <http://biomod.net/>, accessed on 2021-07-07

[8] Kubyshkin, V, Budisa, N (2019) The Alanine World Model for the Development of the Amino Acid Repertoire in Protein Biosynthesis, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, Vol. 20, pp. 5507-5523

[9] Kubyshkin, V, Budisa, N (2019), Anticipating alien cells with alternative genetic codes: away from the alanine world!, *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, Vol. 60, pp. 242–249

[10] Budisa, N, Kubyshkin, V, Schmidt, M (2020), Xenobiology: A Journey towards Parallel Life Forms, *ChembBioChem*, Vol. 21, No. 16, pp. 2225

[11] Diwo, C, Budisa, N (2019), Alternative Biochemistries for Alien Life: Basic Concepts and Requirements for the Design of a Robust Biocontainment System in Genetic Isolation, *Genes*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 17-32

[12] Budisa, N (2014), Xenobiology, New-to-Nature Synthetic Cells and Genetic Firewall, *Current Organic Chemistry*, Vol. 18, No. 8, pp. 936-943

[13] Kuhn, D (1989), Children as intuitive scientists, *Psychological review*, Vol. 96, No. 4, pp. 674-689.

[14] Kuhn, D, Pearsall, S (2000), Developmental Origins of Scientific Thinking, *Journal of Cognition and Development*, Vol. 1, pp. 113-129

[15] Gruber, H (1999), Wie denken und was wissen Experten?, in: *Wissen und Denken: Beiträge aus der Problemlösepsychologie und Wissenspsychologie* (Eds.: W. Mack, W. Ziegler, A), Springer Fachmedien, Wiesbaden, pp. 193-209

[16] Gartmeier, M, Gruber, H, Hascher, T, Heid H (Eds.) (2015), *Fehler. Ihre Funktion im Kontext individueller und gesellschaftlicher Entwicklung*, Waxmann, Münster

[17] Bloom, BS (1976), *Taxonomie von Lernzielen im kognitiven Bereich*. Weinheim und Basel 1976, pp. 200 ff.

[18] Langemeyer, I (2015), *Das Wissen der Achtsamkeit. Kooperative Kompetenz in komplexen Arbeitsprozessen*. Waxmann, Münster

[19] Schmitt, F-J, Schönemann, T, Kruse, F, Egbers, F, Delitzscher, S, Weissenborn, J, Aljanazrah, A, Friedrich, T (2015), Targeted Inversion of the Tutorials in “Mathematics for Chemists”, A Case Study. Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE), pp. 191-200

- [20] Schmitt, F-J, Kruse, F, Egbers, F, Delitzscher, S, Schönnemann, T, Theis, B, Wilkening, S, Moldenhauer, M, Wiehe, R, Willoweit, M, Keuer, C, Aljanazrah, A, Friedrich, T (2017), Effectiveness of Using Interactive Targeted Inverted (IGT)–Education on Students' Learning at the Technische Universität Berlin. Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference, Berlin, pp. 2146-2153
- [21] Aljanazrah, A, Schmitt, F-J, Friedrich, T (2017), Evaluation of the use of flipped classroom based tutorials in “mathematics for chemists” course from students' perspective, in: Research Highlights in Education and Science (eds.: Pehlivan, M, Wu, W), ISRES Publishers, Ames, Iowa, USA, pp. 150-155
- [22] Schmitt, F-J, Schröder, C, Yenice Campbell, Z, Moldenhauer, M, Friedrich, T (2017), Proceedings of the 19th. Annual International Conference on Education, Athens, Greece
- [23] Schmitt, F-J, Yenice Campbell, Z, Schwab, H-J, Weinkauf, M, Schröder, C (2018), Forschendes Lernen in der Studieneingangsphase – die Projektvabore im Orientierungsstudium MINT^{grün}, Greifswalder Beiträge zur Hochschullehre, Vol. 9, pp. 75 ff.
- [24] Mieg, HA, Lehmann, J (2017) Forschendes Lernen: Wie die Lehre in Universität und Fachhochschule erneuert werden kann. Campus Verlag, Frankfurt am Main
- [25] Schmitt, FJ, Frielingsdorf, S, Friedrich, T, Budisa N (2021), Courses Based on iGEM/BIOMOD Competitions Are the Ideal Format for Research-Based Learning of Xenobiology, *ChemBioChem*, Vol. 22, No. 5, pp. 818-825
- [26] Bouquet, F, Organtini, G, Kolli, A, Bobroff, J (2020), 61 Ways to Measure the Height of a Building with a Smartphone, *arXiv:2010.11606*
- [27] web page: <https://thedigitalteacher.com/>, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [28] Arnold, R, Lermen, M, Haberer, M (2017), Selbstlernangebote und Studienunterstützung. Schneider Verlag Hohengehren
- [29] Langemeyer, I, Martin, A (2015), Selbstregulation im Studium, in: Epistemic and learning cultures – wohin sich Universitäten entwickeln (Eds.: I. Langemeyer, M. Fischer, M. Pfadenhauer), Juventa/Beltz, pp. 296-307
- [30] Kuhl, J (2001), Motivation und Persönlichkeit: Interaktionen psychischer Systeme, Hogrefe
- [31] Zimmerman, BJ (1986), Development of self-regulated learning: Which are the key subprocesses?, *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, Vol. 16, pp. 307-313.
- [32] Schmitz, B, Wiese, BS (2006), New perspectives for the evaluation of training sessions in self-regulated learning: Time-series analyses of diary data, *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, Vol. 31, pp. 64-96.
- [33] Wild, KP, Schiefele, U (1994), Lernstrategien im Studium: Ergebnisse zur Faktorenstruktur und Reliabilität eines neuen Fragebogens. Zeitschrift für differentielle und diagnostische Psychologie

- [34] Krapp, A (2002), Structural and dynamic aspects of interest development: theoretical considerations from an ontogenetic perspective, *Learning and Instruction* Vol. 12, pp. 383–409
- [35] v. Wensierski, HV (2015), Technik und Naturwissenschaft im Jugendalter, Budrich
- [36] Fahrenberg, J, Myrtek, M, Pawlik, K, Perrez, M (2007), Ambulatory assessment: Monitoring behavior in daily life settings, *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, Vol. 23, pp. 206–213.
- [37] Loeffler, SN, Myrtek, M, Peper, M (2013), Mood-congruent memory in real life: Evidence from interactive ambulatory monitoring, *Biological Psychology*, Vol. 93, pp. 308-315.
- [38] web page: <http://biomod19.biocat.tu-berlin.de>, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [39] web page: <https://www.facebook.com/igem.berlin/>, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [40] web page: https://twitter.com/iGEM_Berlin, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [41] web page: https://www.instagram.com/igembiomod_berlin/?hl=de, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [42] web page: <http://biomod.net/winners/2017.html>, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [43] web page: <https://www.tu-berlin.de/?118156>, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [44] web page: <http://biomod.biocat.tu-berlin.de>, accessed on 2021-07-07
- [45] de Cazes, M, Belleville, M-P, Petit, E, Sanchez Marcano, J (2016), Erythromycin degradation by esterase (EreB) in enzymatic membrane reactors, *Biochemical Engineering Journal*, Vol. 114, pp. 70-78
- [46] Cobbett, C, Goldsbrough, P (2002), Phytochelatins and metallothioneins: roles in heavy metal detoxification and homeostasis, *Annu Rev Plant Biol.*, Vol. 53, pp. 159-182.
- [47] Martinez, C, de Geus, P, Lauwereys, M, Matthyssens, G, Cambillau, C (1992), Fusarium solani cutinase is a lipolytic enzyme with a catalytic serine accessible to solvent, *Nature*, Vol. 356, No. 6370, pp. 615-618.
- [48] Vonderviszt, F, Namba, K, Structure, Function and Assembly of Flagellar Axial Proteins. *Madame Curie Bioscience Database*
- [49] Schmitt, F-J, Maksimov, EG, Suedmeyer, H, Jeyasangar, V, Theiss, C, Paschenko, VZ, Eichler, HJ, Renger, G (2011), Time resolved temperature switchable excitation energy transfer processes between CdSe/ZnS nanocrystals and phycobiliprotein antenna from *Acaryochloris marina*, *Photon Nanostruct: Fundam Appl*, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp. 190-195
- [50] Schmitt, F-J, Allakhverdiev, SI (2017) Reactive Oxygen Species: Signaling Between Hierarchical Levels in Plants, John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey, USA
- [51] Schmitt, F-J, Yenice Campbell, Z, Bui, MV, Hüls, A, Tomo, T, Chen, M, Maksimov, EG, Allakhverdiev, SI, Friedrich, T (2019), Photosynthesis supported by a chlorophyll

f-dependent, entropy-driven uphill energy transfer in *Halomicronema hongdechloris* cells adapted to far-red light, *Photosynth Res*, , Vol. 139, No. 1-3, pp. 185-201.

[52] Schmitt, F-J, Thaa, B, Junghans, C, Vitali, M, Veit, M, Friedrich, T (2014), eGFP-pHsens as a highly sensitive fluorophore for cellular pH determination by fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), *Biochim. Biophys. Acta : Bioenergetics*, Vol. 1837, No. 9, pp. 1581-1593

[53] Tejwani, V, Schmitt, F-J, Wilkening, S, Zebger, I, Horch, M, Lenz, O, Friedrich, T (2017), Investigation of the NADH/NAD⁺ ratio in *Ralstonia eutropha* using the fluorescence reporter protein peredox, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta: Bioenergetics*, Vol. 1858, No. 1, pp. 86-94

[54] Haas, T, Krause, R, Weber, R, Demler, M, Schmid, G (2018), Technical photosynthesis involving CO₂electrolysis and fermentation, *Nature Catalysis*, Vol. 1, pp. 32–39

[55] Saper, G, Kallmann, D, Conzuelo, F, Zhao, F, Tóth, TN, Liveanu, V, Meir, S, Szymanski, J, Aharoni, A, Schuhmann, W, Rothschild, A, Schuster, G, Adir, N (2018), Live cyanobacteria produce photocurrent and hydrogen using both the respiratory and photosynthetic systems, *Nature Communications*, Vol. 9, pp. 2168

[56] Hu, Y, Rehnlund, D, Klein, E, Gescher, J, Niemeyer, CM (2020), Cultivation of Exoelectrogenic Bacteria in Conductive DNA Nanocomposite Hydrogels Yields a Programmable Biohybrid Materials System, *Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, Vol. 12, No. 13, pp. 14806–14813

[57] Wilkening, S, Schmitt, F-J, Horch, M, Zebger, I, Lenz, O, Friedrich, T (2017), Characterization of Frex as an NADH sensor for in vivo applications in the presence of NAD⁺ and at various pH values, *Photosynthesis Research*, Vol. 133, No. 1-3, pp. 305-315

[58] web page: <https://www.magicalmicrobes.com/products/mudwatt-clean-energy-from-mud>, accessed on 2021-07-07